

Multiple Model Predictor for Type 1 Diabetes

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Abstract: The availability of reliable glucose-insulin models is a key point for both glucose control and hypo/hyperglycemia prevention in type 1 diabetes. This paper introduces an enhanced personalized Multiple Model Predictor (MMP) for glucose prediction, addressing both inter- and intra-patient variability. The MMP is identified using a clinically based cost function to weight differently hypo, hyper, and normoglycemia and a smooth switching mechanism between models is implemented to improve the glucose prediction. Tested on the UVA/Padova simulator, the MMP showed a 113% improvement in prediction accuracy with respect to the state-of-art Daily Model, especially during breakfast, demonstrating its potential for improving glucose management in T1D patients.

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I. Introduction

Type 1 Diabetes (T1D) is an autoimmune disease characterized by high Blood Glucose (BG) levels (hyperglycemia, BG > 180 mg/dL). Insulin delivery to treat it, if excessive, can lead to hypoglycemia (BG < 70 mg/dL). The goal of subjects with T1D is to maintain their glucose level in the euglycemic range [70-180] mg/dL. The most recent and advanced treatment, the Artificial Pancreas (AP), is a closed-loop system composed by a Continuous Glucose Monitor (CGM), an insulin pump and a control algorithm [1]. Model Predictive Control (MPC) has emerged as one of the most promising techniques for glucose control. The core of this technique is the dynamic model used for BG prediction: its predictive performance plays a key role in the overall control performance. The availability of reliable glucose-insulin models is also fundamental to design of Alarm Systems (ASs) to predict adverse events and prevent hypo and hyperglycemia [2-3]. The inter- and intra-patient variability characterizing patients with T1D, may limit the performance of MPC algorithm or ASs synthesized using a unique population model. In order to improve their performance, patient-tailored models are required to deal with the inter-patient variability and have shown promising performances in [4]. However, personalized models present poor prediction performances for patients with significant daily insulin sensitivity variations, making the identification of a single Daily Model (DM) unsuitable for them [5]. This work proposes an enhanced version of the personalized Multiple Model Predictor (MMP) described in [5] to account for patients with significant intra-patient variability. A clinically based cost function is introduced to asymmetrically weight hypo, hyper, and normoglycemia during identification procedure and a softly switching mechanism between multiple models for BG prediction is developed. The procedure is tested on a in silico patient of the UVA/Padova simulator [6] with promising results compare to the state-of-art DM.

II. Material and methods

Patient tailored model identification is a non-trivial task due to inter- and intra-patient variability. Moreover, the synchronization of meals and insulin makes it challenging to distinguish between each of the effects; factors like exercise and illness add complexity as they are hard to measure. A promising method for accurate model identification is the Impulse Response (IR) identification [5], which has shown success with both simulated and real patient data. This method consists in identifying two Transfer Functions (TFs), $G_i(s)$ and $G_d(s)$, such that the Laplace transform of the CGM, $Y(s)$, can be written as:

$$Y(s) = G_i(s)I(s) + G_d(s)D(s)$$

where, $I(s)$ and $D(s)$ are the Laplace transform of insulin and meals, respectively. The IR identification technique is composed of two separate steps: the first one utilizes exciting ad-hoc simulation data (impulse responses) of the average patient of the UVA/Padova simulator, not collectable on real subjects for safety reasons. The model obtained from step 1 is then used as initialization for a personalization carried out in step 2. A constrained optimization problem is formulated to optimize the TFs parameters minimizing a new clinically based cost function defined as:

$$SSR_\eta = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N [\eta(Y) (\hat{Y}(j) - Y(j))]^2}$$

where \hat{Y} and Y are predicted and the real CGM, respectively, with the prediction error weighted by a factor η which asymmetrically weights hypo, hyper, and normoglycemia based on the Blood Glucose Index (BGI) defined in [7] (see Figure 1):

$$\eta(Y) = \left(\frac{BGI(Y)}{100} + 1 \right)$$

$$BGI(Y) = 10[1.509(\ln(Y)^{1.084} - \ln(120)^{1.084})]^2$$

Figure 1: BGI [7] (black line). Glucose target of 120 mg/dL represented by the orange dashed line.

This procedure is carried out for each specific patient to deal with the inter-patient variability. Moreover, it is repeated for each Day Period (DP): breakfast, lunch and dinner) to take into account also the intra-day variability of the insulin sensitivity [5], giving rise to a set of 3 models:

$$\begin{cases} x_b(k+1) = A_b x_b(k) + B_b i(k) + M_b d(k) \\ x_l(k+1) = A_l x_l(k) + B_l i(k) + M_l d(k) \\ x_d(k+1) = A_d x_d(k) + B_d i(k) + M_d d(k) \end{cases}$$

The final glucose prediction, \hat{y} , can be computed as

$$\hat{y}(k) = \alpha C_b x_b(k) + \beta C_l x_l(k) + \gamma C_d x_d(k)$$

where $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0,1]$ determine the switch between the three models. As represented in Figure 2, the softly switching mechanism between multiple models is implemented making two of the coefficients smoothly passing from 1 to 0 and vice versa in the transition period $[\bar{t} - t_{switch}, \bar{t} + t_{switch}]$, with t_{switch} a design parameter.

Figure 2: example of transition between breakfast and lunch: α gradually decreases, while β increases giving gradually more importance to x_l than to x_b in the \hat{y} computation.

III. Results and discussion

The identification is carried on the UVA/Padova simulator, a metabolic simulator approved by the Food and Drug Administration as an alternative to animal testing [6]. This study is focused on a one patient case-study, who showed poor performance in [8] using the DM. The DPs are defined as: breakfast 5 am-12 pm, lunch 12 pm-7 pm, and dinner 7 pm-5 am. The 2-day identification scenario involves 3 meal/day. The DM and MMP predictions have been evaluated on a 29-hour testing scenario including 3 meal/day never seen in the identification dataset. Figure 2 illustrates the results obtained by the proposed MMP and the state-of-art DM in the testing scenario. It is well shown how the MMP is able to better predict the glucose trend in particular during the breakfast DP. In Table 1 the FIT metric defined in [8] is reported to compare the performance of the two models: it is evident how the MMP is capable of improving the prediction performance. In particular, on the entire dataset the MMP increases the FIT by 113%. The main improvement is obtained for breakfast

(69% vs 32%) while in the lunch period no improvements are obtained since the DM is used in this subinterval.

Figure 3: G represents BG from testing scenario, \hat{G}_{DM} and \hat{G}_{MMP} are the prediction of the DM and MMP, respectively.

Table 1: FIT results of the identification per DP.

FIT	All day	Breakfast	Lunch	Dinner
DM	31.9%	31.7%	58.9%	45.0%
MMP	67.8%	50.7%	58.9%	66.4%

IV. Conclusions

In this paper a MMP identification approach is carried out to obtain better glucose predictions for patients with T1D characterized by high intra-day variability. The IR identification technique is enhanced with a nonlinear cost function to focus on fitting extreme glycemia events that could result dangerous if undetected. This method has been applied to an in silico patient which DMs are not well representative [8]. Tests comparing the proposed MMP with the state-of-art have been conducted showing a satisfactory 113% improvement of the MMP over the DM. The breakfast DP showed the most significant improvement. These promising results will be extended to the remaining patients as future development, and a controller equipped with the newly developed MMP is under design to improve the glucose control of T1D patients.

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